

CRITICAL VOID CONTENT OF CF/PEEK THERMOPLASTIC COMPOSITES: IMPACT ON NDT AND MECHANICAL PROPERTIES.

D. Saenz-Castillo^{1,2}, V. García-Martínez¹, S. Calvo¹, F. Rodríguez-Lence¹, A. Güemes²

¹ FIDAMC, Foundation for the Research, Development and Application of Composite Materials. Avda.Rita Levi Montalcini 29, Tecnogetafe, 28906 Getafe, Madrid, Spain.

Diego.saenz@fidamc.es; <https://fidamc.es/home>

² Departamento de Materiales y Producción Aeroespacial, E.T.S.I. Aeronáutica y del Espacio, Universidad Politécnica de Madrid, Pza. de Cardenal Cisneros 3, 28040, Madrid, Spain. Dwed, ,

alfredo.guemes@upm.es, <https://www.etsiae.upm.es/>

Keywords: Thermoplastic, Automatic Fiber Placement, Void content, Ultrasonic testing, Mechanical properties.

ABSTRACT

Void content, ultrasonic NDT and mechanical properties (in-plane shear) of a series of thermoplastic composites CF/PEEK laminates were investigated to study the impact of the porosity on the properties of thermoplastic composites. Three manufacturing technologies were compared: vacuum bag-only in oven, hot-press and laser-assisted automatic fibre placement. The manufactured specimens had a stacking sequence of [+45/-45]_{4S} and porosity was induced by altering the processing parameters, especially the processing temperature. A porosity range of 0.5 to 15% was achieved. Shear strength and modulus of all laminates were reported. Results showed that in-plane shear strength decrease with void content, at different trend for each manufacturing technology. Also, an increase of the ultrasonic attenuation with the void content is reported.

1 INTRODUCTION

Carbon Fibre Reinforced Thermoplastic (CFRTP) composites have been under the spotlight of aerospace industry for many decades. However, it is in this current moment when CFRTP may penetrate in real primary structures of commercial aircrafts. This fact is mainly due to the emergence of new and competitive out-of-autoclave (OoA) technologies, such as the innovative laser-assisted automatic fibre placement (LAFP) with in-situ consolidation system (ISC) [1].

Due to the nature of composite materials manufacturing, it is almost impossible to manufacture complete defect-free structures. One of the most common and harmful defects in composites are the voids or porosity. The impact of voids in composites materials have been deeply studied in the past when it refers to thermoset matrix [2,3] but only few studies can be found regarding the impact of voids in thermoplastic composites [4].

With this aim, a set of carbon fibre/PEEK CFRTP laminates was manufactured by means of three different manufacturing technologies, including vacuum bag only in oven (VBO), hot-press and laser-assisted automatic fibre placement with in-situ consolidation. The key parameters of the process (consolidation temperature, consolidation pressure) were modified from the optimal manufacturing cycle in order to obtain different levels of void content. Void content values were assessed by different methodologies (matrix digestion, 2D microscopy) and compared. The void content was compared with the ultrasonic non-destructive testing (NDT) to perform a correlation. All laminates were subjected to a matrix dominated mechanical testing (IPSS - In-plane shear strength) and also correlated with void values in order to establish a critical void content value where the mechanical properties start to decrease.

Thus, the effect of voids in thermoplastic composites was studied. The correlation of void content with ultrasonic NDT and mechanical properties was performed. The results of the study revealed that each of the manufacturing technologies lead to a different type of voids. Also, mechanical properties of thermoplastic laminates start to decrease at a different critical void content value.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Material

For this study, the selected material consisted in prepreg CF/PEEK unidirectional tape, supplied by Cytec Solvay Group with commercial name APC-2/AS4. Tape 300-mm wide was using for processing in oven and press, while same material but 6.35-mm wide slit material was used for automatic lamination.

APC-2 AS4 has a nominal prepreg fibre areal weight (FAW) of 145 g/m² and theoretical matrix weight fraction of 34%. Ply nominal thickness is 0.135m

2.2 Manufacturing of laminates

A series of 300 x 300 mm laminates of 16 plies with a lay-up of [+45/-45]_{4S} were manufactured for this study. Three different manufactured methods were used, including vacuum bag in oven, hot-press and in-situ consolidation with automatic lamination. In order to induce manufacturing defects (mainly porosity) to the manufacturing laminates, some processing parameters were modified from the optimal consolidation cycle, including temperature and pressure.

Vacuum bag only in oven (VBO)

The CF/PEEK laminates manufactured via vacuum-bag-only in oven under different processing parameters are compiled in Fig. 1. The suffix of each laminate code indicates the processing temperature of each sample. A diagram of the manufacturing set-up is also shown. The process is well known and consists of a vacuum bag with a preform located between two kapton films. A breather is also located to facilitate air evacuation. The external bag is then positioned and fixed with sealant tape. In this case, the modified parameter was consolidation temperature since it is directly related with the resin viscosity. Low temperatures near melting point (343°C) are expected to restrict the air flow during the cycle due to high resin viscosity. Thus, more porosity is expected to be found in the laminates consolidated at low temperatures. A thermocouple was embedded into the laminate for temperature process control. Higher temperatures than 430°C were not studied due to degradation of ancillary materials.

Laminate code	Consolidation temperature (°C)	Vacuum (mbar)	Cooling rate (°C/min)
VBO400 (ref)	400	100	1-2
VBO340	340	100	1-2
VBO350	350	100	1-2
VBO360	360	100	1-2
VBO370	370	100	1-2
VBO430	430	100	1-2

Fig. 1 Processing in vacuum bag only. Manufacturing parameters of the performed consolidation cycles (left). Set-up diagram of VBO manufacturing (right).

Consolidation in hot-press

In this case, a series of laminates were consolidated in hot-press. The CF/PEKK preform is located into a metallic frame which works as a resin container. Two caul plates are located at bottom and top sided to obtain a good quality finish surface. Polyimide release film was used for facilitate demoulding. The processing parameters of the laminates manufactured via hot-press are shown in Fig. 2, along with a diagram of the manufacturing set-up. Manufacturing with hot-press not only allowed performing trials at different consolidation temperatures, but also with different processing pressures. For hot-pressed laminates, a temperature range between 340-500°C was applied, and two extra panels were manufactured modifying the final applied pressure. In this case, low temperatures may also induce porous laminates, but pressure is much higher than vacuum bag processing. Higher temperatures may induce degradation effects on the resin, which could also lead to macro voids. The processing temperature was monitored with an embedded thermocouple connected to a data logger system.

Fig. 2 Processing of laminates with hot-press. Manufacturing parameters of the performed consolidation cycles in press (left). Diagram of the set-up during hot-press manufacturing (right).

Laser-assisted automatic fibre placement (LAFP)

Fig. 3 shows the parameters of the laminates manufactured in-situ consolidation LAFP (left) and a diagram of the manufacturing process (right). The process is mainly focuses on the automatic deposition of a new tape over a substrate. A diode-laser heats up the incoming tape and the substrate over melting point and a compaction roller consolidates the plies. This is a very complex process where many phenomena are taking place like melting of the resin, crystallization, cross-linking of the polymer chains, light reflection, intimate contact and even degradation of the resin when high temperatures peaks are reached.

Processing temperature is one of the parameters governing the process. Thus, some laminates were manufactured at different laser power which led to different processing temperatures. Even though temperature is a key parameter, there are others processing parameters which have been proven to have a great impact of the final behaviour of the part, such as lamination speed or compaction roller [5–7]. Also, cooling rate has a great impact on the final crystallization of the laminates; therefore several strategies can be used to maximize the crystallization, as the use of a secondary laser or heating-tools. For this study, the lamination speed was fixed as a relative low speed of 1 m/min, and self-heating tooling were used at a tooling temperature of 200°C. An elastomeric roller was also used for this study. For the processing temperature control, an infrared thermography camera (FLIR) was used.

In this case, different applied laser power values led to different nip point temperatures. Those temperatures are expected to interfere with the viscosity of the resin and the facility of voids to being compressed. As commented, roller force and lamination speed play a key role in the final mechanical behaviour of the manufactured parts, and will be studied in future work.

Laminate code	Average laser power (W)	Temperature at NIP point (°C)	Roller force (N)	Cooling rate (°C/min)
ISC400	180	340–370	500	10000
ISC370	230	370–400	500	10000
ISC430	300	400–430	500	10000

Fig. 3 Processing of laminates with laser-assisted ATP (LAMP). Manufacturing parameters of the performed consolidation cycles in LAMP (left). Diagram of the set-up during LAMP lamination (right).

2.3 NDT. Ultrasonic testing

All the manufactured laminates were subjected to ultrasonic testing (UT). For the UT, an automated TRITON 8000TT+ (Tecnitest) equipment was used working in double through-transmission with a single probe working as emitter-receiver inside a water tank, shown in Fig. 4. The specimens were located on methacrylate supports over a reflector plate. Typical 5MHz frequency was applied.

Fig. 4 Automated ultrasonic NDT equipment

After the inspection, c-scans registers (attenuation and amplitude) were generated automatically by the equipment for analysis. Ultrasonic testing is usually calibrated with the help of a standard reference block. The gain of the signal is normally adjusted by taken the back-wall echo at 80% of full height on screen (FHS). The evaluation of the flaws is commonly performed by analysing the back-wall echo drop-off or the appearance of intermediate echoes. Thus, a drop of the back-wall echo down to 40% of FHS means a 6dB attenuation and a drop down to 20% indicates 12dB of signal attenuation.

As an example of the generated c-scans, Fig. 5 shows amplitude c-scans of VBO panels manufactured in this study (From left to right: VBO400, VBO360 and VBO340). According to the scale, black areas are more attenuated owing to remaining air inside the structure after the cycle. The analysis of the c-scans suggested that VBO400 (left) is well consolidated, VBO360 (middle) has poor level of consolidation in the centre area of laminate and VBO350 has a very low level of consolidation in most of the laminate.

Fig. 5 Amplitude c-scans of laminates manufactured by vacuum bag-only in oven. VBO400 (left), VBO350 (middle) and VBO360 (right).

For this study, averaged values of attenuation levels were required for correlation, even though the equipment did not provide them. In order to obtain the averaged attenuation values of each c-scan, ImageJ software was used. ImageJ is able to generate colour histograms in grey scale of RGB scale of a given figure. Grey colour scale is made of 255 grey tones from white to black. For this study, grey scale histograms of the c-scans were generated and a translation to attenuation was performed in order to obtain averaged values of the attenuation (in dB).

Fig. 6 Grey colour histograms generated by ImageJ from amplitude c-scans of laminates VBO400 (left), VBO350 (middle) and VBO360 (right).

The histograms analysis suggested that the ultrasonic c-scan is less attenuated by porosity when the peak is more oriented to the right edge of the scale (white). On the contrary, if histogram shape is located to the left edge (black) it meant that is more attenuated because of porosity. Narrower peaks (as VBO400, left in Fig. 6) indicated homogeneous c-scans, mean wider histogram peaks indicated more heterogeneous c-scans, caused by areas with porosity.

2.4 Porosity assessment

The void content of each laminate was calculated after performing matrix digestion method, following EN2564 [8]. A batch with a minimum of three samples extracted from different regions of each laminate was tested. In this method, the sample is weighed before and after the removal of the resin. The void content of each sample was then calculated.

2.5 Mechanical testing

For this study, in-plane shear testing was performed to evaluate the mechanical behavior of the manufactured samples. The tests were performed following EN 6031[9]. Batches of at least six coupons of each laminate were tested. In-plane shear strength (IPSS) was selected for this work because of being a matrix-dominated property. Thus, irregularities in the matrix such as porosity may lead to a drop of the properties and a correlation may be performed.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In this section, all the results are presented and discussed. Table 1 reports the average values of void content of each manufactured laminate and the ultrasonic attenuation (in dB) obtained from image analysis of the generated c-scan during the ultrasonic inspection. A range of 0.6 to 15% of void volume was achieved with the applied methodology. In vacuum bag manufacturing, higher void contents are related with lower processing temperature, which suggests that high viscosity of the resin prevented a proper resin and air flow during consolidation cycles. Thus, air was not evacuated. On the contrary, low void content laminates was achieved at low temperatures during hot-press manufacturing. This may be related to high pressure applied during process. Higher temperatures up to 500°C during manufacturing in hot-press caused larger porosity, maybe due to resin degradation. In the case of ISC-LAFP, a maximum void content of 2.9% is shown. There is a relation of ultrasonic attenuation and void content. Thus, higher void content levels led to higher ultrasonic attenuation. Typical ultrasonic attenuation thresholds applied in aerospace for thin laminates are 6, 12 and 18 dB, depending on the structural application.

Table 1 void content and ultrasonic attenuation (in dB) of the laminates

Vacuum bag-only in oven			Hot-press			In-situ consolidation LAFP		
Laminate	Mean void content (%)	Ultrasonic Att. (dB)	Laminate	Mean void content (%)	Ultrasonic Att. (dB)	Laminate	Mean void content (%)	Ultrasonic Att. (dB)
VBO340	14.5 ± 1.3	18.2	HP340	0.9 ± 0.3	0.5	ISC370	1.6 ± 0.1	2.3
VBO350	3.8 ± 1.9	16.2	HP370	0.8 ± 0.1	0.8	ISC400	2.9 ± 0.9	4.4
VBO360	2.4 ± 1.6	2.5	HP400	1.0 ± 0.3	1.5	ISC430	2.2 ± 0.8	2.2
VBO370	2.2 ± 0.1	2	HP430	2.1 ± 1.6	5.0			
VBO400	1.1 ± 0.3	0.9	HP460	2.7 ± 0.6	9.3			
VBO430	0.8 ± 0.0	1	HP500	9.0 ± 0.5	20.0			
			HP400_0.2	2.7 ± 0.9	2.1			
			HP400_1.5	0.6 ± 0.8	0.4			

The results of the in-plane shear testing (IPS) performed are compiled in Table 2. Again, the results may be compared with the processing parameters (indicated in the laminate name suffix of each laminate).

Table 2 Mechanical shear properties of the laminates: In-plane shear strength

Vacuum bag-only in oven		Hot-press		In-situ consolidation LAFP	
Laminate	In-plane shear strength(MPa)	Laminate	In-plane shear strength(MPa)	Laminate	In-plane shear strength(MPa)
VBO340	32.5 ± 2.8	HP340	164.4 ± 34	ISC370	190.0 ± 5.0
VBO350	88.8 ± 32.0	HP370	175.0 ± 8.4	ISC400	148.0 ± 5.1
VBO360	150.1 ± 3.8	HP400	179.9 ± 12.0	ISC430	154.8 ± 2.2
VBO370	150.5 ± 2.6	HP430	203.6 ± 11.3		
VBO400	222.4 ± 4.0	HP460	186.6 ± 5.6		
VBO430	220.0 ± 6.2	HP500	51.33 ± 3.0		
		HP400_0.2	182.83 ± 4.9		
		HP400_1.5	181.4 ± 16		

In-plane shear modulus and strength of each manufactured laminate are plotted in Fig. 7. Shear strength value of laminate VBO400 (222.4 MPa) manufactured in oven at a processing temperature of 400°C was set as the reference for this study. On average, hot-pressed laminates have a lower shear strength than oven-consolidated laminates, but high elastic modulus can be obtained at elevated temperatures. Regarding the manufacturing with ISC-LATP, the laminate ISC370 manufactured at a lower temperature showed higher strength than the rest of ISC laminates, however, a very low shear modulus was shown, indicating a high plastic deformation of the samples during testing.

Fig. 7 In-plane shear properties (strength and modulus) of the samples manufactured by three different technologies: vacuum-bag-only (top left), hot-press (top right) and in-situ consolidation LAMP (bottom).

The correlation between the void content of each laminate with the ultrasonic absorption coefficient is represented in Fig. 8. The ultrasonic absorption coefficient (dB/mm) was calculated as the product of the ultrasonic attenuation (dB) and the nominal thickness of the laminates (2.16mm). Thus, the trend of higher absorption coefficient at higher averaged porosities can be observed. A dotted line was included for the specimens manufactured in oven and hot-press, but more specimens are required to observe a clear trend in in-situ LAMP manufacturing.

Relative variation of IPSS values with the void content are presented in Fig. 9. For the representation, the maximum IPSS value obtained from all the tests was considered as 100%. Again, a 100% reference value of 222.4MPa corresponding to laminate VBO400 was set. Maximum IPSS value obtained with hot-press manufacturing corresponds to 91.5% of the reference in the laminate processed at 430°C; meanwhile the maximum IPSS value obtained via in-situ consolidation corresponded to a 85% of the reference in oven, obtained from laminate ISC370 processes at a temperature of 370°C at the nip point. However, the low modulus of laminate ISC370 must be considered for engineering applications. From the figure, critical void content levels can be obtained, following same methodology as reported by Costa et al. [10], Thus, critical void content can be defined as the averaged void content when the mechanical properties of the given material start to decrease.

Fig. 8 Relation of void content of the manufactured laminates with absorption coefficient of ultrasonic testing

Fig. 9 Relation of in-plane shear strength with void content of the manufactured laminates

Fig. 9 suggests that each manufacturing process may have an associated characteristic critical void content. Thus, a drop of properties of laminates manufactured in oven start to decrease around 1.1% meanwhile averaged properties of hot-press did not decrease until a higher void content, beyond 2.3%. For a clear trend of in-situ consolidated laminates, more specimens are required.

Nonetheless, it has been shown that the location, size and shape of a void can be even more detrimental to the mechanical properties than the averaged value of void content [11]. Thus, a deeper study of the individual characteristics of voids by 3D tomography is highly recommended. In addition to that, crystallinity also plays a key role

4 CONCLUSIONS

A series of CF/PEEK laminates were manufactured by different methods (oven, press and automated in-situ consolidation). Induced voids were achieved by making modifications to the processing parameters of consolidation cycles. Laminates in a porosity range of 0.5–15% were manufactured by modifications in the processing temperature. In-plane shear strength and modulus have been reported for all the manufactured laminates. The experimental results shown that shear strength drops with the void content in the laminates meanwhile ultrasonic absorption coefficient increased with void content. Higher mechanical strength values were obtained with vacuum-bag-only consolidation in oven, but properties decreased at a low void content (around 1.1%). On the other hand, maximum strength values of hot-pressed laminates are lower when compared to oven, but mechanical properties are maintained with higher void content levels above 2% More laminates are required for the observation of clear trends of in-situ consolidation technology.

Further work with X-Ray computed tomography (CT) is required to study the effect of voids size, distribution and shape in the behavior of the material. In addition to CT scanning, more mechanical testing should be performed, including not only matrix-dominated testing, but also fiber-dominated.

REFERENCES

- [1] Qureshi Z, Swait T, Scaife R, El-Dessouky HM. In situ consolidation of thermoplastic prepreg tape using automated tape placement technology: Potential and possibilities. *Compos Part B Eng* 2014;66:255–67. doi:10.1016/j.compositesb.2014.05.025.
- [2] de Almeida SFM, Neto Z dos SN. Effect of void content on the strength of composite laminates. *Compos Struct* 1994;28:139–48. doi:10.1016/0263-8223(94)90044-2.
- [3] Costa ML, Almeida SFM de, Rezende MC. The influence of porosity on the interlaminar shear strength of carbon/epoxy and carbon/bismaleimide fabric laminates. *Compos Sci Technol* 2001;61:2101–8. doi:10.1016/S0266-3538(01)00157-9.
- [4] Zhang D, Heider D, Advani SG, Gillespie JW. *Out of Autoclave Consolidation of Voids in Continuous Fiber Reinforced Thermoplastic Composites*, Long Beach, CA: 2013.
- [5] Khan MA, Mitschang P, Schledjewski R. Parametric study on processing parameters and resulting part quality through thermoplastic tape placement process. *J Compos Mater* 2013;47:485–99. doi:10.1177/0021998312441810.
- [6] Tierney J, Gillespie JW. Modeling of Heat Transfer and Void Dynamics for the Thermoplastic Composite Tow-Placement Process. *J Compos Mater* 2003;37:1745–68. doi:10.1177/002199803035188.
- [7] Stokes-Griffin CM, Compston P. The effect of processing temperature and placement rate on the short beam strength of carbon fibre–PEEK manufactured using a laser tape placement process. *Compos Part Appl Sci Manuf* 2015;78:274–83. doi:10.1016/j.compositesa.2015.08.008.
- [8] EN 2564 : 1998, German Standard Aerospace series, Carbon fiber laminates - Determination of the fibre,-, resin- and void contents, 1998
- [9] EN 6031:1995, Aerospace Series, Fibre reinforced plastics - Test method - Determination of in-plane shear properties, 1995
- [10] Costa ML, De Almeida SFM, Rezende MC. Critical Void Content for Polymer Composite Laminates. *AIAA J* 2005;43:1336–41. doi:10.2514/1.5830.
- [11] Hernández S, Sket F, González C, LLorca J. Optimization of curing cycle in carbon fiber-reinforced laminates: Void distribution and mechanical properties. *Compos Sci Technol* 2013;85:73–82. doi:10.1016/j.compscitech.2013.06.005.